

MULTI-PORT POWER CONVERTERS TO ENHANCE RESILIENCE IN DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

The distribution grid is undergoing a transformation due to the rise in renewable energy generation. The variability in energy production or the lack of inertia resulting from the displacement of synchronous generators could have a significant impact on grid resilience. Therefore, solutions for reliable green energy generation are required. Multiport Converters are presented in this work as a suitable alternative. In particular, a Multiport Converter structure is presented that guarantees reliable distribution network operation in the presence of various abnormal conditions such as faults or islanding.

INTRODUCTION

The development of renewable energy-based electrical systems is transforming electrical networks [1]. The new renewable generation is massively introduced both at the transmission and distribution levels. Under this new scenario, new challenges emerge in the distribution grids (DGs). At Medium Voltage (MV), medium-scale renewable power plants are connected thanks to its decentralization capacity. At Low Voltage (LV), consumers are also introducing generation through self-consumption systems. Additionally, Direct Current (DC) solutions are proliferating in many applications at all voltage levels [2]. This study examines the potential of Multiport Power Converters (MPC) to enhance the resilience of distribution networks.

A MPC is a power electronics device with more than two ports which allows the integration of both AC and DC components [3], as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual example of a MPC.

Thus, this device can facilitate the integration of new renewable energy power plants and technologies such as

storage or electrical vehicle chargers while keeping the grid quality and security and minimizing or avoiding critical conditions, that might compromise the continuous supply of the users. The introduction of an MPC allows the implementation of many local actions, such as adding Energy Storage Systems (ESS) or connecting feeders, that improve the quality and stability of the grid along with optimization of the operation of the whole system. In addition, MPCs are aimed to reduce the total number of power electronics components or their total size, i.e. the total cost.

Figure 2: LV application example of MPC.

The present work analyzes MPC's contribution to increasing the resilience of DGs. First, the MPC's grid requirements defined by Grid Codes (GC) and standards are explained. Therefore, a possible structure and control for an MPC is explained. Then, a case study is presented as an example to evaluate the operation of the grid during abnormal conditions when an MPC is introduced. The paper presents multiple contingencies and shows how an appropriate MPC control can keep islands operating autonomously after severe disturbances occur. Dynamic simulations in Matlab/Simulink are used to validate the ability of MPC to increase grid reliability.

MULTI-PORT CONVERTERS REQUIREMENTS IN DISTRIBUTION GRIDS

This section explains the expected requirements of MPCs in DGs, especially focusing on faults operation.

MPCs can be used as Soft Open Points to interconnect different distribution lines with controllable power while

providing voltage control in both lines. When very severe disturbances occur, the overall distribution network can be split into multiple islands due to the loss of multiple lines. In this case, the MPC offers the advantage of using embedded ESS or renewable generation supplying the multiple ports and enhancing the system's resiliency by coordinating with the available generation capacity. In case of faults, MPC requirements have to be studied depending on whether one port or more are islanded or not.

Grid support and firewall operation

If a fault occurs and is not isolated, the MPC have to ensure that the ports are connected and give support to the grid as much as possible. Requirements of low voltage ride-through are more detailed in HV systems, but, some distribution network standards [4] define voltage profiles that represent which are the levels at which converters should remain connected. Even the current that MPCs could give during a fault is less than with a synchronous generator (SG), converters are controllable. Therefore more flexibility could be provided [4]. Additionally, MPCs could act as a firewall ensuring that faults are not extended through the grid. With a conventional switch, this firewall capacity cannot be provided. Consequently, MPCs must include the presented requirements to support the grid during temporary faults.

In conventional power systems, Short Circuit Current (SCC) has normally not been an issue due to SGs' overcurrent ability and their voltage source converter behaviour. However, the increase of power electronic devices in the modern grid has produced a decrease in SCC levels, which is a problem for the protections, as they are designed using abnormal current levels. On transmission systems, System Operators require that plants provide fault current to minimise the voltage dip and support the system's stability. This requirement is normally defined as a fault current injection [4]. The injected current could be described as a prioritisation of the reactive or the active current.

Island mode operation

If the system is isolated due to a fault, the MPC may need to operate in island mode, therefore it is no longer connected to any grid. An option to maintain the stability of the fragmented DG is ensuring that the port that is islanded is working in Grid-forming (GFOR) mode. Due to the utilisation of GFOR, the port will define the angle instead of synchronising with the grid. Therefore, the islanded port could still operate with the islanded DG systems, e.g. feeding loads. GCs and standards define some requirements for GFOR operation[5], however, they are especially focused on the loss of stability of the grid due to the displacement of Synchronous Generators. Hence, thanks to MPCs, consumption could be supplied during isolation until loads are reconnected to the distribution network.

MULTI-PORT CONVERTER STRUCTURE

Converter Topology and Modelling Assumptions

The requirements presented in the previous section could be satisfied with the MPC and the control presented in this section. The MPC studied in this paper is a non-isolated 3-port structure with two AC-DC ports and one DC-DC port, as shown in Figure 3. The AC-DC ports are based on a two-level voltage source converter (2L-VSC).

Figure 3: Control structure of the 3-port MPC

The ports are represented with average models i.e. without including the switching operation of the converters, which is enough to capture the dynamic response. On the AC side, the AC-DC ports are modelled with an LC filter and a three-phase controlled voltage source. Apart from that, the grid and the lines are modelled with RL circuits. On the DC side, the converter port is modelled as a current source. A capacitor is included in the common DC bus.

Converter Control

Both AC-DC ports have been defined as a master-slave control structure, therefore one port controls the DC voltage (V_{dc}^*) and the reactive power (Q^*), while the other port controls the active power (P^*) and the reactive power (Q^*) [2]. The control structure used in both ports is a classical cascaded control with inner current control as defined in [6]. Moreover, ports could operate in Grid-following (GFOL) or GFOR modes. In the case of GFOL operation, both AC-DC ports operate with a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) that synchronizes the converter with the grid. In the case of GFOR mode, a P-f droop is used to obtain the angle of the grid. Apart from that, with GFOR mode, a voltage loop is used to calculate the current references for the current control loops. It should be mentioned that the reference currents are saturated in both operation modes to ensure that the converter is always working inside the feasible physical limits. To ensure current support during faults, a Fault Current Injection block is used to introduce reactive current during the faults, as defined in [7]. AC-DC ports control is shown in Figure 4.

On the other hand, the DC-DC port has a cascaded control with an active power outer loop and an inner current control, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: AC-DC control.

Figure 5: DC-DC control.

VALIDATION OF MPC OPERATION IN ABNORMAL CONDITIONS

The abnormal operation of an LV DG with an MPC is validated in this section. The studied system has two feeders connected to a common AC grid. Both feeders have been defined with different Short Circuit Ratios (SCR) to represent different distances from the main AC grids. The feeders have loads connected to represent possible LV consumptions, as shown in Figure 6. Notice that the feeders have switches that could be opened when a fault exists. Therefore, AC-DC ports could be islanded. Faults are studied near the slave control port (P_2). If faults occur near the master control port, some modifications in the controllers are required. However, due to space limitations, this case is not presented in this work.

Figure 6: Studied scenario.

To show the capabilities of MPCs, in the studied system an AC balanced fault is studied between 2.8 s and 3 s. Apart from that, a battery connected to the DC part could be considered. The presented control design ensures that the DC voltage is controlled by the battery when available. Therefore, the following tests are presented:

- Test 1: AC balanced temporary fault with battery and switches closed during all the test.
- Test 2: AC balanced temporary fault without battery and switches closed during all the test.

- Test 3: AC balanced permanent fault without battery and switches S_{21} and S_{22} opened after the fault is detected.

AC-DC ports could operate in two modes: Grid-following (GFOL) or Grid-forming (GFOR). In the studied scenarios ports are always working on GFOL, except when a port is islanded, in which case the port operates in GFOR mode. Therefore MPC ports' operation in Test 1 and 2 is summarized in Table 1.

Port	$t < 2.8s$	$2.8s < t < 3s$	$t > 3s$
P1	GFOL	GFOL	GFOL
P2	GFOL	GFOL	GFOL

Table 1: Test 1 and 2 AC-DC ports operation.

In the scenario studied in Test 3, the MPCs' ports operation is defined in Table 2.

Port	$t < 2.8s$	$2.8s < t < 3.05s$	$t > 3.05s$
P1	GFOL	GFOL	GFOR
P2	GFOL	GFOL	GFOL

Table 2: Test 2 AC-DC ports operation.

The parameters used are defined in Table 3. Equivalent impedance is calculated as:

$$Z_{eq} = \frac{U^2}{S_{cc}} \quad (1)$$

Where, $SCR = \frac{S_{cc}}{S_{c-N}}$. Therefore, equivalent resistance R_{eq} and inductance L_{eq} are:

$$R_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{Z_{eq}^2}{1 + \frac{1}{R/X^2}}}, L_{eq} = \frac{R_{eq}}{R/X \cdot 2\pi f_1} \quad (2)$$

The AC grid impedance is defined using a SCR of 10. In the feeders, the equivalent impedance varies depending on the SCR.

Test 1: Battery available and switches closed

In this first test, an AC balanced fault occurs between 2.8 s and 3 s. Additionally, the battery is connected during all the simulation. Switches are not opened in this case, however, due to the MPC the DG is controlled during and after the fault. Notice that fault detection is represented by adding a delay of 10 ms.

Important events are defined in the results (Figures 7 and 8) as:

- 1: Fault starts ($t=2.8$ s).
- 2: Fault is detected ($t=2.81$ s).
- 4: Fault ends ($t=3$ s).
- 5: Fault end is detected ($t=3.01$ s).

Normal operation is ensured as results demonstrate that the converter perfectly follows its references. During faults, converter currents are saturated due to physical limits. Reactive current is prioritized because the battery maintains

Parameter	Value
Nominal AC grid voltage, V_{ac-N}	400 V
Nominal port power, S_{c-N}	300 kVA
Nominal DC bus voltage of MPC, V_{dc-N}	800 V
Short Circuit Ratio, SCR_1, SCR_2	10, 5
R/X ratio, R/X	12.25
AC-DC active power references, P_1^*, P_2^*	0.66 p.u., -0.66 p.u.
AC-DC reactive power references, Q_1^*, Q_2^*	0.33 p.u., -0.33 p.u.
DC voltage reference, V_{dc}^*	1 p.u.
DC-DC active power reference, P_3^*	-0.33 p.u.
Grid impedance, R_g, L_g	$0.7R_{eq1}, 0.7L_{eq1}$
Feeder 11 impedance, R_{11}, L_{11}	$0.15R_{eq1}, 0.15L_{eq1}$
Feeder 21 impedance, R_{21}, L_{21}	$0.15R_{eq2}, 0.15L_{eq2}$
Feeder 12 impedance, R_{12}, L_{12}	$0.15R_{eq1}, 0.15L_{eq1}$
Feeder 22 impedance, R_{22}, L_{22}	$0.15R_{eq2}, 0.15L_{eq2}$
Coupling impedance, R_l, L_l	0.01 p.u., 0.2 p.u.
Capacitor filter, C_f	0.15 p.u.

Table 3: Case study parameters

Figure 7: Test 1 results.

the DC voltage stable. The power of the battery varies to ensure DC voltage stability. Finally, it could be seen that the DC voltage does not have significant variations during

the test, which is crucial as if the DC bus is not available, MPC could not exchange energy between ports.

Test 2: No battery and switches closed

In this second test, the scenario is as in Test 1 but without a battery, as it could be discharged or unavailable. Therefore, DC voltage is controlled by P_1 .

Figure 8: Test 2 results.

Normal operation is again guaranteed as converter signals are tracking their references. When a fault occurs and no battery is available, the master port (P_1) now prioritizes the active current to maintain the DC bus voltage stability. The other results show the same behaviour as with Test 1.

Test 3: No battery and switches opened after fault

In this third test, a balanced permanent fault starts at 2.8 s. When the fault occurs, S_{21} and S_{22} are opened with a delay of 100 ms. Therefore, port P_1 is islanded. Island mode detection time is 150 ms, as defined in [8]. Thus at 3.05 s, the control mode is changed to GFOR when the island mode is detected, as explained in Table 2. Once P_2 operates in island mode, the active power references are 0.

Important events are numbered to facilitate the understanding of the results:

- 1: Fault starts ($t=2.8$ s).
- 2: Fault is detected ($t=2.81$ s).
- 3: S_{21} and S_{22} are opened ($t=2.9$ s).

- 4: Operation mode in P_2 is changed to GFOR ($t=3.05$ s).

Figure 9: Test 3 results.

Results are shown in Figure 9. When the fault starts and is not islanded, P_1 still has voltage available. Therefore, active and reactive currents adapt their values to ensure the system's stability. On the other hand, P_2 voltage is 0 before the isolation of the fault. Due to the island operation and the GFOR operation, the voltage in P_2 is increased when the switches are opened until the mode of operation is changed to GFOR. Consequently, voltage has a transient until, thanks to the outer voltage control, it is stabilized to its nominal value. Currents are saturated, giving priority to the reactive current until the fault is isolated. When the fault occurs P_1 and P_2 active power references are 0, however, the active power measurements are 10 kW after the isolation, as ports change energy between them to ensure that the loads are fed. Reactive power in P_1 could follow its reference value after the opening of the switches. On the other hand, in P_2 the reactive power is -100 VAR to feed the isolated load. Additionally, DC voltage remains stable during all the simulation. Finally, when GFOR mode is activated, a transient appears due to the change of operation mode.

CONCLUSION

Multiport converters (MPCs) have been presented as a suitable solution to improve the resilience of distribution networks, with a particular focus on AC faults. The requirements vary depending on whether the MPC remains connected and supports the grid during the fault, or whether one or more ports are isolated. An MPC based on two AC ports with AC-DC converters and one DC port with DC-DC converter and battery has been studied. The control structure of the AC-DC ports is based on a master-slave configuration. MPC can provide fault ride through capabilities during faults if switches are not opened. On the other hand, during island operation, the ports could supply the loads even when disconnected from the main AC grid.

MISCELLANEOUS

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REFERENCES

- [1] Daniel E. Olivares et al. Trends in microgrid control. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 5(4):1905–1919, 2014.
- [2] Nilanjan Ray Chaudhuri et al. System frequency support through multi-terminal dc (mtdc) grids. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 28(1):347–356, 2013.
- [3] Daniele Falchi et al. On chain-link based multi-port converters able to connect hvdc and mvdc to ac transmission network. In *EPE'22 ECCE Europe*, pages 1–10, 2022.
- [4] IRENA. *Grid codes for renewable powered systems*. IRENA, 2022.
- [5] ASNZS. *Grid connection of energy systems via inverters, Part 2: Inverter requirements*. ASNZS, 2020.
- [6] Egea-Alvarez et al. *Active and Reactive Power Control of Grid Connected Distributed Generation Systems*, pages 47–81. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2012.
- [7] Martí Domínguez Hernández et al. Fault ride through control of multiport converter for distribution grids. In *2022 ISGT-Europe*, pages 1–5, 2022.
- [8] Reza Sirjani and Chinedu Frank Okwose. Combining two techniques to develop a novel islanding detection method for distributed generation units. *Measurement*, 81:66–79, 2016.